
USE OF ICT IN LIBRARIES FOR LIBRARY SERVICES

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Abstract:

Information and communication technology is the boon for library. Library accepts all the changes in the community and gives the best services with the help of all new technologies. In this paper discussed about use of ICT in libraries and libraries gives services to their user as per their need and saves the time of both library staff and user. With the help of ICT library gives services more and more effectively within Covid19 lockdown period.

Key Words: *Information and communication technology, Library services, Web based service*

Introduction:

The present age is considered to be the age of information. New information is being created in every field in every corner of the world. Information that seemed new till the one hour seems old and new faculties are emerging today with new additions to that information. With the advancement of science, new technologies are being developed. This technology has also brought about a drastic change in the information sector. Information that was earlier available only in print form is now available in electronic form as well.

A library is a social institution. It is necessary to preserve knowledge or information for the benefit of the society. Naturally, economic, educational, social and similar events, morals and preferences of the society have an effect on the library. A library is the soul of an institution. The more the library is used, the more the knowledge increases. The needs of the readers are going to change. The variety of

searches and tools become available for the readers or users of the library. The library or librarianship definition changes in this information era. Improvements in the means by which knowledge is collected and disseminated have had a profound impact on increased librarianship.

Impact of ICT on Libraries:

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) plays very important role in the services provided by libraries. Advances in information technology have brought about revolutionary changes in human life and society. The impact of information technology increased the efficiency of researchers and thus accelerated national development by promoting agricultural, industrial, educational, political, cultural and human development. Although there has been an explosion of knowledge, the sphere of knowledge has expanded rapidly due to information technology. Due to

information technology, education has become socially oriented. Technology and professional education has increased due to ICT. Libraries are also being influenced by ICT.

The use of information technology has become mandatory in the library. Libraries have to stay updated to cater to the growing and changing needs or demands of the growing readership. The traditional functions of libraries are changing. Academic libraries play an important role in the education process today.

In our education system there is a direct relationship between students and teachers as well as other factors. This includes the library. Libraries work to connect students and information. Now the format of the exam has also changed and the previous exam method is no longer there but the exam is conducted online and only multiple choice questions are asked in it. Students need accurate information for this exam. Libraries are also trying to provide this information. Information technology has been adopted by the library and that is why libraries have always been at the forefront in providing services to students and other readers.

Due to the progress in the field of information technology, the modern electronic tools and media that have come into existence today pose a challenge to the libraries to use these media. Responding to this challenge, libraries have started providing library services more effectively with the help of these media. That is, considering this challenge as an opportunity rather than a crisis, libraries have been able to provide innovative library services.

Use of ICT in Libraries:

Library Automation: Library automation is made easy with the help of computers. If library automation is there then information of every book is stored and made available to the users in very less time. Because of this it saves time of reader and library staff too.

Online Library Membership: Library registration form is also filled through Google Form and they are given library membership. For that, students do not feel the need to come to the library during this period. This service become very useful in the Covid-19 lockdown period.

Library Orientation Programme: Library orientation programme is made effective with the use of power point presentation. After admission of the students, they are being helped to introduce the library in this lockdown through Zoom or Google Meet App and the students are also informed about the books in the library, the rules of the library, the library timings.

Information Literacy training: In today's age of competition, a huge amount of information is available on the internet at a click, but readers do not understand exactly what information to take for their use. Here the role of library becomes important. Librarians need to train readers how to search for information, guide them and find the exact information they want, how to evaluate and analyze it and how to use it, and this training is very useful for readers in today's situation. This information literacy training is also give online with the use of various apps.

Instant Messaging Service: This service is provided using mobile or some messaging site. This service can be used to take a book requested by a user from the library, to return a book, to inform the user about the changed hours or holidays of the

library. The notices of library are given with the use of this service instantly.

E-mail can be used as a communication tool for librarians. E-mail has become the most common form of communication in daily life. Libraries use it to communicate with other library staff and users. E-mail can be used to send reminders about overdue books, new book arrivals, exhibition notices and programs etc.

Whatsapp is very popular app allows you to group your users and send them useful information to these groups. This is proving very useful in the current situation. In this we can deliver some pdf or previous year question papers directly to the students on demand.

Online Book Exhibition- This online book exhibition is very useful in the Covid 19 lockdown. In that situation, while celebrating various days, it is not possible to display the books in the library which have the importance of that day, so virtual books were displayed in many places, so it has helped the students to know the books in the library. The students also got to know the new books through the exhibition.

Virtual tours can be organized with the help of information technology. Through that, the students can get the experience of getting information by visiting various places in this current situation and getting the information through audio-visual media helps the students to understand easily.

CAS & SDI Service: With the help of information technology, the information about the new collections in the library is being conveyed to the students at a fast speed. Under SDI service, it is possible to provide services to certain users easily and quickly.

OPAC: Online Public Access Catalogue is the service for getting information about library books. It has become possible for the user to get the information about the books or non-book materials in the library from any place at any time. For that, there is no time limit for coming to the library.

Reference Service: With the use of various apps librarian gives effectively reference service to library user. A library user can ask the librarian any time about his information and the librarian can give him the book where he can get the information he needs.

Institutional Repository: Now most of the libraries have created Institutional Repository. It contains the brochure and annual issue of the organization. In this you can see the notes prepared by the professors of the college as well as the videos that are useful with the course. Previous year question papers, question banks as per their syllabus are made available for the students. All this information has made it possible for students to get information at any time and study using it.

E document delivery service: With this service, it is easy to send the information required by the reader in PDF or other e-format through e-mail. While providing this service we may provide some information to our readers for educational purposes considering copyright.

Along with this, the libraries have also informed their readers that they have taken some e-resources by paying subscriptions and they can use that information by guiding them in their proper use and giving them a password.

QR code: By using QR Code we can give our readers a link to a website in less time. Also through this we can give the information of the book to the readers. It is also useful in the marketing of library,

means that every reader get information in very less time.

Library Websites: Most of the institutions have now created library websites. It has become possible to easily convey many types of information to the readers. It provides information about the library. Information about library timings, services provided by the library and staff working in the library is also given in this. Online membership, Previous year question papers, syllabus, Web OPAC is made available for library users. Many libraries gives information about svarious courses in many places during the lockdown period and have put useful information for various courses on their websites. These include SWAYAM online courses, UG/PG MOOCs, e-PG Pathshala, e-Content courseware in UG subjects, SWAYAMPURABHA, CEC-UGC YouTube channel, National Digital Library, Shodhganga, e-Shodh Sindhu. In Ask Librarian, readers can ask about the information they want and it is possible to provide them with the information they want. Along with this, some magazines and newspapers are available online and the readers can use it anytime by giving its link on your website.

Conclusion:

The traditional libraries are going through tremendous changes because of ICT. The use of ICT has become mandatory in the library. Libraries have to

stay updated to cater to the growing and changing needs or demands of the growing readership. Libraries have provided many good services with the help of information and communication technology so that the student can easily reach to the process of acquiring knowledge.

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